

Thread-based microfluidic sensor for lithium monitoring in saliva

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Figure S1. Actual photos of μ TADs for: (A) 10^{-4} and (B) $0.95\text{mol}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ lithium standards, demonstrating color change of the sensing area from blue to magenta. (C): A photo of the experimental setup.

Figure S2. Influence of the buffer's pH on the measuring range of μ TADs. The measuring range is here defined as a difference between H coordinate measured for $10^{-1} \text{ mol}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ and $10^{-6} \text{ mol}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ lithium standards, $n = 3$. The cocktail composition used is indicated in Section 2.2, DOS was employed as a plasticizer.

1. μ TADs optimization

1.1. Plasticizer selection

A plasticizer-free cocktail, composed of 16.7 mg PVC, 0.5 mg ETH 5294, 0.44 mg lithium ionophore VI and 0.74 mg KFMPB, was prepared in 1 mL freshly distilled THF. 5 mg of the following plasticizers: dioctyl sebacate (DOS), o-nitrophenyloctyl ether (NPOE) and tributyl phosphate (TBP) were then added to 150 μ L portions of cocktail. Prior to deposition on thread, the cocktail was diluted 4-fold in THF. μ TADs were assembled according to Section 2.2 and calibration curves were registered for each cocktail.

1.2. Cocktail dilution optimization

TBP-based cocktail (composition indicated in the previous section) was used to study the influence of its dilution factor on μ TADs response towards lithium. The cocktail was diluted 2-fold, 3-fold or 4-fold (i.e. 1:1, 1:2 and 1:3) with THF prior to deposition on thread. Calibration curves were registered for each cocktail and the results are shown in Fig. S2. 3-fold dilution provides the widest measuring range with the biggest precision, so it was selected for further experiments.

Figure S3. The influence of cocktail dilution on the response of μ TADs towards lithium, $n = 3$.

1.3. Lipophilic salt content optimization

To optimize lipophilic salt content while maintaining other cocktail components at a fixed level, a cocktail containing 16.7 mg PVC, 33.3 mg TBP, 0.5 mg ETH 5294 and 0.44 mg lithium ionophore VI was prepared in 1 mL of THF alongside with KFMPB stock solution in THF (10 mg·mL⁻¹). Then various quantities of KFMPB stock solution were added to the base cocktail to obtain cocktails of the following chromoionophore (I) to salt (R⁻) to ionophore (L) ratios: 1:1:1.5; 1:1.25:1.5 and 1:1.5:1.5. These cocktails were diluted 3-fold with THF and deposited on thread. The registered calibration curves are shown in Fig. S3. Cocktail with 1:1.25:1.5 ratio was selected for further experiments.

Figure S4. Calibration curves registered using cocktails with differing lipophilic salt content, $n = 3$. I – lipophilic pH indicator (chromoionophore); R – lipophilic salt; L – ionophore.

1.4. Ionophore content optimization

To optimize ionophore content while maintaining other cocktail components at a fixed level, a cocktail containing 16.7 mg PVC, 33.3 mg TBP, 0.5 mg ETH 5294 and 0.92 mg KFMPB was prepared in 1 mL of THF alongside with ionophore stock solution in THF (5.0 mg·mL⁻¹).

Various quantities of ionophore stock solution were added to the base cocktail to obtain cocktails of the following chromoionophore (I) to salt (R^-) to ionophore (L) ratios: 1:1.25:1.0; 1:1.25:1.5, 1:1.25:1.75 and 1:1.25:2.0. These cocktails were diluted 3-fold with THF and deposited on thread. The registered calibration curves are shown in Fig. S4. Cocktail with 1:1.25:1.5 ratio was selected for further experiments.

Figure S5. Calibration curves registered using cocktails with differing ionophore content, $n = 3$. I – lipophilic pH indicator (chromoionophore); R^- – lipophilic salt; L – ionophore.

2. Selectivity study

Selectivity study was conducted using separated solutions method. This method relies on measuring the response of the tested sensor to a potential interferents in the absence of an analyte. The calibration curves were obtained for sodium, potassium and ammonium ions in the concentration range from 10^{-6} to $0.95 \text{ mol}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$. The obtained results are shown in Figure 2 in the main manuscript.

Boltzmann sigmoidal function was fitted to the response curves. Logarithms of selectivity coefficients ($\log K_{X(I)-Li(I)}^{opt}$) were calculated as a horizontal distance between a response curve for lithium and for interfering ion. This distance was measured at the degree of chromoionophore protonation $(1-\alpha)$ equal 0.5 [1].

The required selectivity was calculated using the following equation [1]:

$$K_{ij,max} = \frac{c_{i,min}}{c_{j,max}} \cdot \frac{P_{ij}}{100}$$

assuming maximum tolerable error (P_{ij}) of 10%, the lowest lithium concentration ($c_{i,min}$) of 1 $\text{mmol}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ and the maximal possible concentrations of interferents ($c_{j,max} = 75 \text{ mmol}\cdot\text{L}^{-1} \text{ Na}^+$, 23 $\text{mmol}\cdot\text{L}^{-1} \text{ K}^+$, 2.3 $\text{mmol}\cdot\text{L}^{-1} \text{ Ca}^{2+}$, 0.4 $\text{mmol}\cdot\text{L}^{-1} \text{ Mg}^{2+}$ and 0.12 $\text{mmol}\cdot\text{L}^{-1} \text{ NH}_4^+$ [2]).

3. TOPO content optimization

To optimize TOPO content in the sensing cocktail while maintaining other cocktail components at a fixed level a cocktail without TOPO and without plasticizer was prepared. This cocktail composed of: 16.7 mg PVC, 0.5 mg ETH 5294, 0.5 mg lithium ionophore VI and 0.92 mg KFMPB in 1 mL THF. Stock solutions of TOPO (10 $\text{mg}\cdot\text{mL}^{-1}$) and NPOE (50 $\text{mg}\cdot\text{mL}^{-1}$) were also prepared in THF. Cocktails with varying TOPO and NPOE contents were prepared to achieve compositions given in Table S1. Using μTADs sensitized with these cocktails response curves to lithium, sodium and potassium ions were registered (Fig. 3 and Fig. S5). Cocktail **3** was selected as the optimal one.

Table S1. Tested cocktails compositions, given in weight percentages.

Cocktail component	1	2	3	4
TOPO	0.0%	1.5%	2.0%	5.0%
NPOE	64.5%	63.0%	62.5%	59.5%
ETH 5294	0.9%	0.9%	0.9%	0.9%
Li ionophore VI	0.9%	0.9%	0.9%	0.9%
KFMPB	1.7%	1.7%	1.7%	1.7%
PVC	32%	32%	32%	32%

Figure S6. Optimization of TOPO content in sensing cocktail in terms of μTADs response to potassium ion, $n=3$.

4. Selectivity study for μTADs TOPO/NPOE cocktail

The selectivity study was conducted according to the description in Section 2, using separated solutions method. μTADs response towards sodium, potassium, ammonium, magnesium and calcium ions was registered. The obtained curves are shown in Fig. S6.

Figure S7. The responses of μ TADs towards lithium and interfering ions: sodium, potassium, ammonium, magnesium and calcium, $n = 3$.

5. Kinetic studies

To register reaction kinetics and establish an optimal equilibrating time, instead of photos, a video was recorded using a usual experimental setup and camera parameters (given in Section 2.2 in the main manuscript). From the video individual frames were cut with Avidemux software. The frames were cut every 1 s for the initial 10 seconds after sample introduction, then every 10 s up to 1.5 minutes, and every 30 s for the remaining time. The obtained this way JPG files were analyzed with ImageJ software, according to Section 2.2 in the manuscript). The kinetics are shown in Figure S7 for two aqueous lithium standards – 1 and 32 $\text{mmol}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$.

Figure S8. The influence of equilibration time on the registered signal (reaction kinetics) for low (1 mmol·L⁻¹) and high (32 mmol·L⁻¹) lithium concentrations.

Figure S9. Lifetime of lithium selective μ TADs stored in a black desiccator tested with $3.2 \text{ mmol}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$ lithium standard. Dashed lines represent a 95% confidence interval.

Figure S10. Bland-Altman plot for lithium determination in saliva samples with the developed μ TADs and flame photometry as a reference method.

6. References

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